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Innovative Terrain Mapping: A Comparison of Drone and iPhone + viDoc Techniques

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Abstract—This study presents a comparison of two different surveying methodologies aimed at terrain modeling. The first approach involved a drone equipped with multispectral sensors, while the second utilized an iPhone combined with the viDoc RTK Rover for data acquisition, which enables the creation of high-accuracy 3D models by generating geo-referenced images in real time. The comparison was possible thanks to precise georeferencing, achieved by performing NRTK (Network Real Time Kinematic) surveys of control points placed near the area of interest and visible in both drone and iPhone-acquired images. The difference between the two-point clouds was evaluated by performing point-to-point distance comparisons, while digital elevation models (DEMs) were compared in a GIS environment using pixel-by-pixel subtraction. The analysis revealed that the differences in point positions between the two surveys were within a few centimeters, with variations primarily attributed to sensor and environmental factors. Similarly, the elevation differences between the DEMs were also in the centimeter range, indicating high precision in both methods. These findings demonstrate that both technologies can provide accurate terrain models, with minor differences that are typically within the acceptable range for many precision agriculture and land management applications. The results underscore the strengths and limitations of each technology, offering insights into their practical applicability for field surveying.

I. INTRODUCTION

Terrain modeling is a crucial aspect for the monitoring of environmental changes due to natural (such as soil erosion) and anthropic causes (such as tillage). Recently, [1] compared the capability of a drone equipped with a multispectral sensor to that of Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS) for assessing interrill soil erosion in agricultural plots under different soil management practices, leveraging the multispectral sensor's ability to distinguish vegetation within the plots. The first results showed a good performance of multispectral drone. Therefore, [2] tested the effects of the vegetation on the morphological reconstruction of the surface. The study showed that the presence of a crop could negatively affect the terrain model.

Other studies, instead, have compared UAV photogrammetry surveys with airborne and terrestrial laser scanning surveys to obtain high-resolution elevation data for monitoring terrain changes. [3, 4].

This paper aims to test a new rapid and low-cost method for terrain surveying, comparing it with the commonly used approach of UAV photogrammetry for this type of investigation. A viDoc RTK rover by Pix4D, integrated with an Apple iPhone 15 Pro

Max, was used to model the survey area and was compared to a UAV-based method. Currently, the main applications of this system are in the field of cultural heritage [5, 6]. Only a few studies have been conducted in other sectors, such as road mapping [7, 8], environmental surveying [9], and to test the accuracy of the instruments [10]. The goal of this work is to assess the use of the viDoc RTK rover in terrain mapping for small-scale agricultural and hydraulic applications, as an alternative to UAV-based methods.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study area

The study was conducted at SERLAB, the experimental site of the University of Perugia's Department of Agricultural, Food, and Environmental Sciences, located 20 km south of Perugia in Umbria, central Italy. The site includes ten plots (dimensions: 8×22 m, 4×22 m, 4×11 m, and 2×11 m) aligned with the 16% maximum slope. The soil, classified as Calcaric Cambisol with a silty-clay-loam texture, is monitored for runoff and soil loss after erosive events (events producing measurable runoff). Hydraulic boundaries, made of galvanized steel sheets embedded 0.25 m into the soil and reinforced with metal stakes, direct runoff into storage tanks for measurement. Precipitation data are recorded at 5-minute intervals. For this study, six plots were surveyed using UAV photogrammetric techniques and an integrated iPhone + viDoc approach, both conducted simultaneously in November 2024 (Figure 1). The land had been previously prepared, and at the time of the survey, it exhibited scattered vegetation. To georeference the surveys, 14 checkerboard targets (GCPs – Ground Control Points) positioned around the plots were surveyed using GNSS technique in NRTK mode with a Topcon Hiper HR receiver.

Figure 1. Study area and GCPs position (yellow points)

B. Photogrammetric UAV survey

Image acquisition was performed using a DJI Phantom 4 RTK Multispectral UAV (including six $\frac{1}{2}$.9-inch CMOS sensors: one for RGB imaging and five covering spectral bands blue, green, red, red edge, and near-infrared) (Figure 2a). A sunlight sensor on the UAV adjusts for real-time irradiance, enhancing data accuracy. An integrated D-RTK GNSS receiver ensures centimeter-level

camera positioning accuracy. Flight planning, executed via DJI GSPro on an Apple iPad, used a polygon grid at 10 m altitude, with 75% image overlap and a speed of 2 m/s in "Hover & Capture" mode. A total of 425 images were acquired with a GSD (Ground Sample Distance) of 0.5 cm/pixel. The DJI D-RTK2 GNSS receiver provided additional accuracy, supporting multiple satellite systems (GPS, BEIDOU, GLONASS, and Galileo) for stable performance in diverse conditions.

C. iPhone + viDoc survey

The survey was also conducted using an Apple iPhone 15 Pro Max equipped with the viDoc RTK Rover (Figure 2b). The viDoc RTK Rover is a German-designed GNSS rover that includes an RTK antenna and is specifically designed to be compatible with Apple devices equipped with LIDAR sensors. When combined with the Pix4Dcatch app, it enables the creation of high-accuracy 3D models by generating RTK-accurate, geo-referenced images in real time. Each plot was surveyed individually by manually moving the equipment around it in a full loop. For every plot, an average of 398 images were acquired.

Figure 2. DJI Phantom4 Multispectral (a) and Apple iPhone 15 Pro Max with viDoc RTK Rover (b)

D. Point clouds and DEMs generation

The 425 UAV-acquired images were processed using Agisoft Metashape Professional (v.1.7.5) with the Structure from Motion (SfM) photogrammetric method. Of the 14 targets surveyed, 10 were used as Ground Control Points (GCPs), while the remaining 4 served as Check Points (CPs). The resulting point clouds contained approximately 200 million points, with an average of around 135000 points per m^2 . The average error was 0.030 m on the GCPs and 0.046 m on the CPs positions. The reconstruction of data acquired with iPhone + viDoc was performed using Pix4Dmatic software. A dense point cloud can be generated from the RGB images, while the depth map can be obtained from the LiDAR data. The two datasets were then unified into a single fused point cloud obtaining an average of approximately 235000 points per m^2 . For consistency with the point cloud generated from the UAV survey, the same 14 targets were used to georeference the cloud obtained from the iPhone data, with an average error of 0.024 m on the GCPs and 0.038 m on the CPs positions. Both point

clouds generated from the two surveys were subjected to a noise reduction filter, which was particularly necessary due to the presence of grass in the plots, a likely contributor to the noise, especially in the iPhone-derived clouds. For subsequent analysis, the plots were aligned and clipped to the same shape, removing the edges where the weeds were most dense (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Point clouds with RGB values obtained by UAV (a) and iPhone+viDoc (b)

Both point clouds obtained from UAV and iPhone + viDoc surveys were processed with Cloud Compare (v.2.13) to generate raster-based Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) with 1 cm of resolution.

E. Comparison between point clouds and DEMs

To evaluate the differences between the two surveys (drone-based and iPhone + viDoc), point cloud comparisons were performed using Cyclone 3DR software, leveraging the “cloud-to-cloud” inspection tool to assess spatial discrepancies and quantify variations between the datasets. The comparison considered both the three-dimensional positions of the points and their discrepancy along the three axes (N, E, H). In addition, Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) derived from both methods were compared through a pixel-by-pixel subtraction performed in QGIS. This method allowed for the identification of localized variations and overall trends in terrain representation between the two survey techniques.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figures 4 and 5 show the results of the comparison between the two point clouds and the two DEMs, derived from UAV and viDoc data, respectively. In the first case, since the evaluation was based on the distance to the nearest points between the two point clouds, only positive differences are observed. In contrast, the DEMs comparison was performed through pixel-by-pixel subtraction, resulting in both positive and negative values.

Figure 4. Comparison between UAV and iPhone+viDoc point clouds (3D)

Figure 5. Difference between DEMs obtained by UAV and iPhone+viDoc

In Table I the differences (m) obtained from the “cloud-to-cloud” comparison between the point clouds derived from UAV and iPhone+viDoc surveys, considering the 3D points position, are reported. The monitored plots result coupled, i.e. the plot 4 could be considered the replicated of the plot 1 (same dimension, same slope and the same soil management), so the results can be analyzed considering the similar plots (plot 6 vs plot 2, plot 1 vs plot 4 and plot 5 vs plot 3). The statistical parameters of the differences showed a good accordance between the plot 6 and 2 and the plot 5 and 3. For the plot 1 and 4 more differences are found.

TABLE I. STATISTICAL DIFFERENCES (M) (MEAN, 10TH PERCENTILE AND 90TH PERCENTILE) DERIVED FROM THE COMPARISON CLOUDS TO CLOUDS BETWEEN UAV AND IPHONE+VIDOC POINT CLOUDS

Cloud to cloud (3D positions)	3D points position Differences (m)					
	Plot 1	Plot 2	Plot 3	Plot 4	Plot 5	Plot 6
Mean	0.018	0.019	0.016	0.033	0.019	0.020
10 th percentile	0.005	0.003	0.002	0.010	0.003	0.003
90 th percentile	0.031	0.034	0.033	0.054	0.041	0.041

In Table II the differences (m) obtained from the Z-axis (elevation) comparison between the point cloud derived from UAV and iPhone+viDoc surveys were reported. This comparison was reported to evaluate the effect of the DEM interpolation on the elevation differences.

In Table III the differences (m) obtained from the DEMs derived from UAV and iPhone+viDoc surveys are reported.

TABLE II. STATISTICAL DIFFERENCES (M) (MEAN, 10TH PERCENTILE AND 90TH PERCENTILE) DERIVED FROM THE COMPARISON CLOUD TO CLOUD ALONG THE Z-AXIS (ELEVATION) BETWEEN UAV AND IPHONE+VIDOC POINT CLOUDS

Cloud to cloud (Z-axis)	Points positions Differences (m) along Z-axis					
	Plot 1	Plot 2	Plot 3	Plot 4	Plot 5	Plot 6
Mean	0.017	0.031	0.004	0.032	-0.014	-0.001
10 th percentile	0.001	0.008	-0.022	0.007	-0.040	-0.032
90 th percentile	0.031	0.051	0.030	0.054	0.011	0.031

TABLE III. STATISTICAL DIFFERENCES (M) (MEAN, 10TH PERCENTILE AND 90TH PERCENTILE) DERIVED FROM THE COMPARISON DEMS OBTAINED BY UAV AND IPHONE+VIDOC

DEMs	Elevation Differences (m)					
	Plot 1	Plot 2	Plot 3	Plot 4	Plot 5	Plot 6
Mean	0.021	0.039	0.007	0.040	-0.017	-0.003
10 th percentile	0.009	0.025	-0.016	0.021	-0.039	-0.033
90 th percentile	0.032	0.055	0.030	0.057	0.005	0.026

Comparing Tables II and III, it is demonstrated that considering DEMs or Z-axis differences have no influence on the final result as the obtained values are comparable. The mean values are around 2 centimeters for all plots when considering the 3D positions, while the DEM differences reach a maximum of 4 centimeters. Even if higher, both comparisons show mean values comparable to measurement errors.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the tested methodology proved to be a valid tool for agricultural applications, especially those involving terrain modeling or, for example, the definition of geometric characteristics of vegetation. The 3D models obtained through viDoc survey are characterized by high accuracy and resolution and are already metrically corrected, with proper scale and orientation. In particular, the use of NRTK corrections enables the creation of a model that is directly georeferenced in a global reference system with centimeter-level accuracy. Apart from being less expensive compared to traditional ground measuring equipment, the main advantage of using the viDoc RTK rover integrated with an Apple smartphone is the ability to combine RGB and LiDAR data in a single, small, handheld, and lightweight device, thus optimizing both data acquisition and processing time. Therefore, for small areas, as demonstrated in the presented case study, the use of the viDoc RTK rover can be particularly valuable for fast surveys. Additionally, unlike drone flights, it is not subject to regulatory constraints related to operator permits and specific areas. However, it should be noted that for larger areas, a traditional UAV survey is always recommended. The first important result showed that the presence of vegetation influences

the quality of the point clouds by introducing higher level of noise. This situation can be worsened due to the wind effect. What was also noticed is that the presence of metal around the plots generates multiple reflections especially when it comes to Lidar reconstruction. This is why a good practice is removing a small buffer around metal objects. The different sizes of the analyzed plots seem not to have any impact on the results. In fact, the differences are around a few centimeters, in accordance with the measurement errors.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Vinci, A., Brigante, R., Vergni, L., Tosti, G., Marconi, L. Innovative technologies for monitoring interrill erosion, in L. Sartori et al. (Eds.): MID-TERM AIIA 2024, Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, 586, pp. 1-9, 2025. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-84212-2_1
- [2] Vinci, A., Brigante, R., Vergni, L. in press. Soil loss estimation under different soil management using a multispectral UAV, 2024 IEEE Workshop on Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry (MetroAgriFor), Padova, Italy.
- [3] Grohmann, C. H., Garcia, G. P. B., Affonso, A. A., Albuquerque, R. W., 2020. Dune migration and volume change from airborne LiDAR, terrestrial LiDAR and Structure from Motion-Multi View Stereo, Computers & Geoscience, Volume 143, 104569, ISSN 0098-3004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2020.104569>.
- [4] Guisado-Pintado, E., Jackson, D. W. T., Rogers, D. 2018. 3D mapping efficacy of a drone and terrestrial laser scanning over a temperate beach-dune zone. Geomorphology, Volume 328, pp. 157-172, ISSN 0169-555X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2018.12.013>.
- [5] Rapuca A. and Matoušková E, 2023. Testing of close-range photogrammetry and laser scanning for easy documentation of historical objects and buildings parts. Stavební Obzor - Civil Engineering Journal, 32(4), 504-518. <https://doi.org/10.14311/CEJ.2023.04.0038>
- [6] Aksoy, E., 2025. Determining the usability of the viDoc device, which integrates with smart phones, in documenting historical structures. Measurement, 242, Part D, 116156, ISSN 0263-2241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2024.116156>
- [7] Suleymanoglu, B., Tamimi, R., Yilmaz, Y., Soyacan, M., and Toth, C., 2023. Road infrastructure mapping by using iPhone 14 pro: an accuracy assessment. Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLVIII-M-1-2023, 347–353. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-M-1-2023-347-2023>
- [8] Tamimi, R. and Toth, C., 2023. Performance assessment of a mini mobile mapping system: iPhone 14 Pro installed on a e-scooter. Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLVIII-M-3-2023, 307–315, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-M-3-2023-307-2023>
- [9] Chauvin, S., 2023. Water Table Height and Microtopography in Swamps of Southeastern Michigan as Influences of Black Ash Tree Establishment and Survival in the Presence of Emerald Ash Borer. Honors College Theses. 80. <https://digitalcommons.wayne.edu/honorsthesis/80>
- [10] Tamimi, R., Relative accuracy found within iPhone data collection, 2022. Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLIII-B2-2022, 303–308. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B2-2022-303-2022>